

THE NEED TO IMPROVE THE ETHNO-PEDAGOGICAL SYSTEM OF PREPARING FUTURE PEDAGOGUES FOR SPIRITUAL EDUCATION ACTIVITIES

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Abstract: This article analyzes the improvement of the ethno-pedagogical system of preparing future pedagogues for spiritual education activities, and its necessity today is detailed. The importance of the most advanced and unique ideas and opinions of folk pedagogy, which is one of the spiritual cultures of our people, is explained.

Key words: pedagogue, spiritual education, ethnopedagogy, system, improvement, analysis and synthesis, modeling, axiological, reflexive, ethnology, pedagogy.

Introduction.

Today, preparing future pedagogues for spiritual education has become one of the priority tasks. In particular, the fact that Uzbekistan has entered a new era of development based on the idea of "From national revival to national rise", the reforms in the wide-scale socio-economic and spiritual-educational spheres carried out in society are, first of all, the basis for the development of our country. integration in the fields of science, education, and in particular, reforms in the development of modern higher education are becoming a great national goal, a national movement.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS

The possibility of spiritual-cultural, educational heritage, folk pedagogy in ensuring personal development in Uzbekistan, scientists V. Y. Zohidov, N. M. Mallayev, I. N. Mominov, A. Rustamov, M. M. Khairullayev, Sh. M. Shomuhamedov, T. A. Egamberdiyeva; directions of folk pedagogy of spiritual, moral, cultural education of the individual, pedagogic scientists A. Zunnunov, N. Masharipova, O. Musurmonova, D. Muqimova, S. Nishonova, N. Ortikov, M. Salayeva, O. Safarova, R. .Safarova, O.Hasanboyeva, D.Kasimova, Z.Gurbanniyozova, M.Kuronov, A.Ibrohimov, H.Sultonov, G.I.Makhmutova, N.Jorayev, B.Ziyomukhamedov, S.Ziyamuhamedova, S.Kadirova, I.Suvonkulov in their works, literary scholars M. Alaviya, M. Jorayev, O. Ma'dayev, T. Mirzayev showed the moral and educational aspects of examples of folk oral creativity, musicologists O. Ibrohimov, F. Karomatov who scientifically based the educational aspects of folk songs.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The head of our state said at the video selector meeting held on January 19, 2021 on the issues of fundamental improvement of the system of spiritual and educational work and strengthening the cooperation of state and public organizations in this regard, "if the body of society's life is the economy, its soul and spirit is spirituality. As we decided to build a new Uzbekistan, we rely on two strong pillars. The first is a strong economy based on market principles. The second is a strong spirituality based on the rich heritage of our ancestors and national values" [3].

Crime, corruption, fraud, hypocrisy, lying, egocentrism, moral corruption, family discord, loss of affection, blind imitation of "popular culture", indifference, alienation, The spread of vices such as adultery, irresponsibility in raising children, crisis of family values, indifference to the fate of the country increases the need to improve the ethno-pedagogical system of national education. In particular, one cannot be indifferent to the fact that the processes of globalization create new opportunities for humanity, as well as unexpected problems. Because threats and dangers against the national identity and moral values are becoming more and more intense in these same global processes. At the same time, it is not a secret that thinking only about oneself, looking lightly at work and family, consumerism is being inculcated in the minds of people, especially young people, in various ways.

Spiritual education is manifested in an integral connection with the nation's history, way of life, future, generations, social layers, national consciousness, language, spirituality and culture.

The main goal of spiritual education is to gradually form such important qualities as loyalty to the motherland, entrepreneurship, fortitude, ideological immunity, kindness, responsibility, tolerance, legal culture, new thinking, and hard work in young people, starting from childhood 30 It is important to develop and implement a mechanism of mutual effective cooperation of parents, caregivers, teachers, continuing education institutions and the neighborhood community in the implementation of continuous spiritual education that lasts up to the age of 10 years. The main task was to develop the knowledge and skills of the population on child education, pedagogical skills, to regularly acquaint citizens with innovative pedagogical technologies, methods and forms of implementation based on the world experience of continuous spiritual education. Also, formation of a healthy worldview against malicious information, vices that destroy morals, destructive ideas that lead young people astray,

organization of continuous moral education is to effectively establish cooperation between state organizations, civil society institutions, mass media and the private sector [4]. That's why it is important to carry out scientific-technological reform of youth education in our country on the basis of spiritual education on a modern basis, to form it on the basis of scientifically based basic competencies and qualities based on today's needs.

A new, systematic approach to education, in the guaranteed formation of basic qualities in young people, family, preschool education, general education, secondary special vocational and higher educational institutions, to fully reveal the socio-pedagogical possibilities of neighborhoods and among them requires raising the scientific-methodological integrity to a new level. Loyalty to the motherland, duty and responsibility, initiative and other qualities remain as theoretical concepts in the minds of young people, but they do not become practical habits in their nature. As a result, there is a discrepancy between their words about these qualities and their actions, which causes a number of problems for young men and women who enter independent life every year to find their place in life. The lack of formation of high goals, self-mobilization to study, insufficient development of the qualities of will, perseverance, diligence, and action in some students also harms the quality of education [5]. Therefore, spiritual education as an integrative feature of a person combines spiritual knowledge, the ability to determine one's place in the system of spiritual values, and the ability to demonstrate spiritual maturity in a wide range of life situations. The main functions of this skill include: axiological, directional and managerial. The structure of spiritual skill development appropriately includes the following components: introductory-analytical, value-oriented, reflexive-active. These components also reflect the social description of spiritual competence: information with spiritual content is analyzed and evaluated from the point of view of universal human values, creatively compatible with personal-spiritual values, in a form convenient for understanding other people. It is necessary to be expressed, to be developed on the basis of evidence based on the consideration of different options of spiritual values, to make the right movement within the framework of moral reflection and a wide range of life situations. In turn, these components serve as indicators of the development of spiritual skills in students.

In introducing such new approaches to education, in the development of the spiritual education system, it is appropriate to make effective use of the

opportunities of ethnopedagogy, theoretical foundations of ethnopedagogical values and sources.

At each stage of human history, the direction of development is determined on the basis of the methodological unity of socio-economic development. This law was a factor in the development of science, art, culture, production and lifestyle, which are forms of social consciousness based on socio-economic views, ideas and ideals prevailing in the society. In this way, during the historical development, the rich spiritual heritages collected in connection with the education and upbringing of a well-rounded person have found their expression in the folk pedagogy. Therefore, in the preparation of future pedagogues for the process of spiritual education, it is this spiritual heritage - by introducing them to the main ideas of ethnopedagogy related to education, that they acquire the knowledge, skills and qualifications that prepare the ground for effective use in pedagogical activities. It is necessary to focus on medicine.

In the training of future pedagogic personnel, it is necessary to focus on acquiring the knowledge, skills and qualifications that prepare the ground for effective use in pedagogical activities by introducing them to this spiritual heritage - the main ideas of ethnopedagogy.

The peoples of Central Asia, in particular, the Uzbek people and their cultural and educational development have developed over the centuries, the ideas of education embodied the essence of social and political processes of different periods. These enlightened thoughts and ideas created by our people, the rich heritage of education and training have brought up thousands of generations in the spirit of universal virtues. Therefore, it is not for nothing that ethnopedagogy, which is the heritage of our ancestors, is called a rare field of folk wisdom and etiquette.

Ethnopedagogy has played an important role in the moral, educational formation and maturity of our ancestors for centuries. For example, the nation reflected its spiritual-educational, artistic-aesthetic views, philosophical-ethical concepts, vital, educational-educational conclusions in its ethno-pedagogy. An important direction of ethnopedagogy is the implementation of national-spiritual education, and one of its important features is to ensure the preservation of national characteristics. In this sense, the main goal of ethnopedagogy is to develop the pedagogical thinking of the future pedagogical personnel, to organize the teaching process of our people and the rich spiritual and educational heritage and pedagogical views collected on the theory of

education, educational and educational to increase their professional-pedagogical training by introducing them to their possibilities.

The ethno-pedagogical system aimed at preparing future pedagogues for the process of spiritual education is based on:

spiritual-educational and national values of our people;

child education in the family, education methods, methods and tools;

moral norms of the Uzbek people, culture of behavior;

the reflection of nature and human relations, healthy lifestyle in folk pedagogy;

pedagogical ideas of the great thinker;

the educational value of folklore and epics;

the role of national customs, ceremonies, traditions, traditions, folk games and toys as a means of education;

religious teachings in folk pedagogy;

folk arts, crafts, etc. in folk pedagogy.

The main goal of the ethno-pedagogical system aimed at preparing future pedagogues for the process of spiritual education is the formation and expansion of pedagogical thinking in future pedagogical personnel, the organization of the teaching process of our people and the rich spiritual- to gain their professional and pedagogical training by introducing them to their educational heritage and pedagogical views, educational opportunities.

Ethnopedagogy is a direction about the educational experiences of ethnic groups, their spiritual, inner and outer views on the ancient values of family, clan, generation, and nation. It shows ways of using folk pedagogy in modern conditions, collects and implements experiences of ethnic groups in this regard. In other words, ethnopedagogy can be seen as the theoretical basis of education of different peoples. In all nations, qualities such as extraordinary intelligence, politeness, bravery, honesty, hard work, love for the country, and loyalty to the people are highly valued. Therefore, ethnopedagogy is a scientific direction formed between pedagogy and ethnology, which promotes the comparative study of traditional folk pedagogy, methods of child education, the use of games and folklore [2]. In this study, educational work in all directions is conducted based on the ethnopedagogical approach.

Ethnopedagogue G.N. Volkov stated that "Stereotype descriptions emphasizing the strong and unique aspects of each nation have not lost their importance to this day" [1]. These include positive qualities such as German orderliness, American business, French politeness, English formality, and Uzbek hospitality.

The great pedagogues of the past paid a lot of attention to studying the pedagogical views and pedagogical experiences of the people. Classical pedagogues claim that ethnopedagogy enriches approaches and theoretical foundations of education, serves as its support and basis. Pedagogical sciences could not suppress pedagogical views from the everyday life of the people, just as oral creativity was not eliminated by the creation of fiction. Pedagogical sciences and ethnopedagogy interacted, positively influenced each other's development, and as a result, a pedagogical culture was created.

Russian writer V. G. Belinsky, who is very interested in the pedagogical culture of nations, says: "The uniqueness of each nation is mainly its worldview, religion, language, customs and traditions." The great philosopher Hegel compared the intellectual wealth accumulated in the past to "the mother earth, which radiates strength from itself." He stated that "every innovation of science and education originates from its appeal to antiquity." Therefore, the traditionality of culture, including pedagogical culture, is an important sign of the high culture of peoples. The great scholar Abu Nasr Farabi says: "The awakening of interest and attention of our people to their ancient culture is a proof of their true wisdom" [6]. Therefore, ethnopedagogy is a collection of experiences and knowledge of education, which have been collected in the course of people's life activities and passed from generation to generation.

CONCLUSION. People of Central Asia, including the Uzbek people, are creative people who create material and spiritual wealth like other peoples. Masterpieces of science, art and literature of our forefathers, great scholars, who have matured through the study of folk pedagogy, which is an integral part of a multifaceted historical and rich culture, have taken their rightful place among the treasures of world culture for many centuries. . The most advanced and unique ideas and opinions of folk pedagogy, which is one of the spiritual culture of our people, the methods, tools, skills and qualifications used in education have not lost their value and importance even in our time.

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